

THE IMPORTANCE OF MANAGEMENT IN THE HEALTH CARE

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Annotation:

Today, public health protection is only we all know that it is not the duty of health organizations. This is generally the work of the state and society, but the health care system plays an important unifying and coordinating role in managing this process. Public health is the provision of comprehensive health care based on the needs of a specific population group. Therefore, it is necessary to have information on determining the appropriate resources based on the state of public health. Therefore, the essence of Public Health is to strengthen the health of the population, prevent, diagnose and treat diseases, as well as physical, social and occupational placement. is to determine personnel, various medical devices and tools necessary for providing medical services.

Key words: Medical services, health care, medical service provision, medical assistance, management styles, management process, healthcare system.

Аннотация:

Сегодня охрана здоровья населения - это только всем известно, что это не обязанность медицинских организаций. В целом это работа государства и общества, но важную объединяющую и координирующую роль в управлении этим процессом играет система здравоохранения. Общественное здравоохранение – это оказание комплексной медицинской помощи с учетом потребностей определенной группы населения. Поэтому необходимо иметь информацию об определении соответствующих ресурсов исходя из состояния здоровья населения. Поэтому сущностью общественного здравоохранения является укрепление здоровья населения, профилактика, диагностика и лечение заболеваний, а также физическое, социальное и профессиональное размещение. заключается в определении персонала, различных медицинских приборов и инструментов, необходимых для оказания медицинских услуг.

Ключевые слова: Медицинские услуги, здравоохранение, оказание медицинских услуг, медицинская помощь, стили управления, процесс управления, система здравоохранения.

Health Organization Management -is a complex process based on choice optimal solutions, with constant consideration both internal problems of the organization and changing economic and political situations. The terms healthcare management and healthcare administration are often mistakenly used interchangeably, and many people believe they are the same thing. They are two different things. Healthcare management is in charge of the entire healthcare organization while healthcare administration takes care of the staff and employees. The healthcare administrator may be in charge of hiring staff for a specific department, but it's the healthcare manager who may determine if another employee should be hired. In short, healthcare managers deal mostly with the business side of healthcare organizations.

Health care - social, aimed at protecting the health of the population system of economic and medical activities. Health and disease prevention treatment, creation of healthy living and working conditions, high work ability and provides general measures to ensure longevity; its main task is modern, specialized and suitable for patients is to provide assistance. Public, private and public health care in the Republic of Uzbekistan a single healthcare system consisting of the sum of other systems applies. Each country has its own issues of health care of its population pays attention. The health of the population is not only supported by the state besides, the health care system of the state is reasonable and planned should be active in the system. In Health care to carry out this system management activity is of particular importance.

As we know from history, our great grandfather Amir Temur intelligently planned health care to protect the health of the population developed the system and supervised its implementation.

One of the main areas of health care system reform is medical directly related to the organizational structure of the aid model and In order to reduce indirect losses, the health care system is intensive new for the purpose of development and efficient use of existing resources is the development of economic mechanisms. This, in turn, provides medical services restructuring and wide application of new methods of medical service provision requires achievement.[1]

The transition to market relations also brings new demands on the health sector put In particular, reducing the costs of administrative management; patients use of low-cost and effective methods during treatment; Transferring part of the work volume of hospitals to polyclinics, less efficient places reduce

the number; receiving payment for works performed on the basis of the contract and other measures are being taken.

From 1998, a new period in the development of health care began - on November 10, 1998, by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan 1998 - In 2005, the State Program for Reconstruction of the Healthcare System was adopted. It shows measures to improve the quality of medical care for the country's population given Strengthening the primary link of health care based on this program and general medical practice development activities were implemented. Everyone extensive networks of QVP were established in the regions, resulting in two-stage, QVP and the provision of medical assistance through the district central hospital was launched.

A healthcare manager should also be able to use the following management styles: authoritarian; liberal; democratic; bureaucratic.

Authoritarian - this is a leadership style that absolutizes power in one hand. He assumes total denial of collegiality in decision making. Authoritarian style guides in daily activities should not be confused with the administrative-authoritarian style, effectively.

Liberal - (formal, anarchic, condoning) The leader stands apart from his team, minimal intervention in the work of subordinates and the team as a whole, low level of demands employees as well as to yourself. In such a situation, the authorities, as a rule, used by informal leaders.

Democratic - decentralization of management, collective decision making, the initiative of subordinates is supported and actively encouraged. In manager's relationship with subordinates note tact, patience, benevolence

Bureaucratic - In this style, the manager pays more attention to paper documents than to initiative.

Currently, not only one of these management methods, but all of them are used partially depending on the situation.

The main purpose of management is the material and moral of the society in order to fully satisfy their needs, they increase their social relations difficulties, obstacles, problems can be encountered. Management process in terms of its composition, it forms an interdependent and non-stop cycle and it consists of several steps:

1. Goal setting, problem analysis and decision making.
2. Ensuring the implementation of the decision.
3. Control of the implementation of the decision.
4. Analysis and evaluation of the obtained results.

Health care organization is the science of health care management based on optimal methods, a new form of work in various medical institutions and methods, improving the quality of medical services, economic and management develops solutions to problems and the continuity of public health is a piece. Thus, public health and public health organization is a science about the laws of society's health, and its The main goal is to scientifically justify the state of public health raising the level of health status and the quality of medical services provided effective management of the healthcare system in order to improve it organization.

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